

Efficient data management in a BIM-based framework for circularity of products and materials

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Abstract

The Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry is one of the substantial contributors to environmental degradation and resource depletion. Therefore, over the last few years there has been a growing emphasis on sustainability, prompting a shift towards more responsible practices. Digitizing the sector is one of the major ways of streamlining the business and construction practices, making it more efficient and enabling better management of resources. Building Information Modelling (BIM) has been a transformative tool for enhancing sustainability in the built environment. The study reviews the current state of the construction and demolition practices, legal framework, industry standards in the European and Portuguese context, highlighting the challenges of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) management within the AEC industry. This research explores the integration of BIM in the context of information interoperability, demolition, and deconstruction planning, as well as the reuse and recycling potential of construction and demolition waste materials.

The research also seeks to aid the RecycleBIM project, a multi-stakeholder effort aimed at developing an integrated framework for circularity of materials of construction and demolition using BIM methodologies. It develops specifically on the formulation of appropriate informa-

tion requirements and modelling standards based on ISO 19650:2018 and EN 17412-1-1:2020 requirements that guarantee a standardised, interoperable framework that enables asset owners to specify their information demands. The role of open format Industry Foundation Class (IFC) for interoperability and as information containers for circularity are explored. The specific objectives of the dissertation are (i) Development of Product Data Templates for BIM objects and materials for circularity of information. (ii) Creating a Level of Information Need framework based on EN 17412-1 for all major building elements in a Deconstruction Information Model (DIM). (iii) Developing Exchange Information Requirements (EIR) template for a digitized deconstruction process, which includes an inspection, building survey using laser scanning and creation of a BIM model. (iv) Defining a workflow for automated validation of IFC models using Information Delivery Specification.

Recording the circularity parameters and information pertaining to reuse and recycling facilitates the use of CDW as secondary materials and the potential use of existing building stock as material banks. The developed PDTs, Level of Information Need Framework and the EIR template contributes to the growing body of knowledge surrounding sustainable construction practices. It emphasizes the critical role that BIM technology can play in advancing the industry's efforts towards a more responsible, resource efficient and environmentally friendly demolition and deconstruction process.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/PiA_ukWuaHY

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034112